

Osteotoxicity of 3-methylcholanthrene in fish

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Abstract

Many chemicals produced by human activities end up in the aquatic ecosystem causing adverse developmental and reproductive effects in aquatic organisms. There is evidence that some anthropogenic chemicals disturb bone formation and skeletal development but the lack of suitable *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems for testing has hindered the identification of underlying mechanisms of osteotoxicity. Several fish systems – an *in vitro* cell system to study extracellular matrix mineralization and *in vivo* systems to evaluate bone formation and skeletogenesis – were combined to collect data on the osteotoxic activity of 3-methylcholanthrene (3-MC), a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon. Anti-mineralogenic effects, increased incidence of skeletal deformities and reduced bone formation and regeneration were observed in zebrafish upon exposure to 3-MC. Pathway reporter array revealed the role of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor 2 (Ahr2) in the mechanisms underlying 3-MC osteotoxicity in mineralogenic cell lines. Analysis of gene expression in zebrafish larvae confirmed the role of Ahr2 in the signaling of 3-MC toxicity. It also indicated a possible complementary action of the pregnane X receptor (Pxr) in the regulation of genes involved in bone cell activity and differentiation but also in xenobiotic metabolism. Data reported here demonstrated the osteotoxicity of 3-MC but also confirmed the suitability of

fish systems to gain insights into the toxic mechanisms of compounds affecting skeletal and bone formation.

Keywords

osteotoxicity; extracellular matrix mineralization; caudal fin regeneration; opercular bone; skeletal deformities; AHR/PXR signaling pathways

Introduction

A number of studies have reported the probable osteotoxicity – the impairment of bone formation, mineralization and remodeling – of environmental pollutants, e.g. bone loss in cadmium-exposed animals (Bhattacharyya, 2009), delayed ossification and skeleton malformation in mice exposed *in utero* to vanadium (Domingo, 1996), reduced bone growth in pesticide-exposed mice (Pikaliuk, 1991), disrupted skeletogenesis in TCDD-exposed medaka fish (Dong et al., 2012), and bone and joint damages in fluoride-exposed humans (National Research Council, 2006). *In vitro* cell systems capable of bone formation (osteoblast) or resorption (osteoclast) have also been used to characterize underlying mechanisms of osteotoxicity of tributyltin (Koskela et al., 2012; Tsukamoto et al., 2004), TCDD (Koskela et al., 2012), 3-methylcholanthrene (Naruse et al., 2002; Naruse et al., 2004) and di-2-ethyl hexyl phthalate (Bhat et al., 2013).

Among environmental pollutants, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are of particular importance since they are ubiquitous in the environment (they are found in air, water, and soil), some being persistent in soils and sediments and others bio-accumulating in the food chain. PAHs are released into the air mostly from the incomplete combustion of organic materials and vehicle exhausts, and to water and soils from industrial processes and discharges. They are present in the priority lists of chemicals to be monitored for risk

assessments and studied for a better understanding of their mechanisms of action in the United States and in Europe (lists are available from environmental protection agencies at www.epa.gov and www.eea.europa.eu). Several studies have shown that 3-methylcholanthrene (3-MC) – a PAH congener with tumorigenic (Lehner et al., 2017; Levin et al., 1979; Sims, 1967) and immunotoxic (Lubet et al., 1984; Reynaud and Deschaux, 2006) activities – inhibited mouse osteoblast proliferation and differentiation *in vitro*, caused a delay in ossification of the forelimb, hindlimb, and cervical and thoracic vertebrae in fetal mice (Naruse et al., 2002) and inhibited the formation of osteoclast-like cells (Naruse et al., 2004). As part of its tumorigenic activity, 3-MC may induce osteosarcoma at sites of bone fracture in mice (Watanuki et al., 1967) and tumors resembling myositis ossificans – heterotopic calcification in injured muscle – after intrathymic injection of rats with 3-MC-treated cells (Mauffray et al., 1994).

However, studies on PAH osteotoxicity are still scarce and almost entirely done in mammalian systems. There is a need for more experimental data, from different experimental systems and in non-mammalian organisms, e.g. aquatic systems since PAHs are often present in the aquatic environment. *In vitro* and *in vivo* fish systems suitable for studying molecule osteotoxicity are available (Laizé et al., 2014; Fernández et al., 2018) and have been used in the present study to investigate the osteotoxic effects of 3-methylcholanthrene, focusing on its mineralogenic, skeletogenic and osteogenic effects.

Materials and methods

Chemical solutions

A stock solution of 3-methylcholanthrene (Sigma-Aldrich) was prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; Sigma-Aldrich) at 10 mg/mL and was diluted to selected concentrations

into Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM; Invitrogen-Gibco), zebrafish embryo medium (EM; Westerfield, 2000) or fish water (see parameters below).

Cell culture and extracellular matrix mineralization

Gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) vertebra-derived and mineralogenic cell line VSa13 was maintained in DMEM supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Sigma-Aldrich) at 33°C under a humidified 10% CO₂ atmosphere, as previously described (Pombinho et al., 2004). Extracellular matrix (ECM) mineralization was induced by exposing confluent cultures to 4 mM calcium chloride, 10 mM β-glycerophosphate and 50 μg/mL of L-ascorbic acid (Marques et al., 2007). Culture medium and 3-MC treatment (0.1 mg/L) were renewed twice a week and mineral deposition was determined through alizarin red S (AR-S; Sigma-Aldrich) staining and spectrophotometric quantification (Viegas et al., 2012).

Zebrafish larval rearing

An in-house breeding colony of adult wild-type zebrafish (AB strain) aged between 6 and 18 months was used for egg production. It was maintained in a water re-circulating system (ZebTEC, Tecniplast) with controlled water parameters (28 ± 0.1°C, pH 7.5 ± 0.1, conductivity 700 ± 50 μS, NH₃ and NO₂ lower than 0.5 mg/L, NO₃ at 5 mg/L) and under a 10:14 h dark/light photoperiod. After fertilization, eggs were observed under a dissecting microscope and non-fertilized, asymmetrical, vesicle-containing or damaged eggs were discarded. At 5 days post-fertilization (dpf), larvae were fed once a day with live *Artemia* (strain AF, INVE Aquaculture, approximately 5 nauplii per mL). Juveniles were fed daily with dry flake food (Benelux NV) and live *Artemia*.

Zebrafish operculum assay

In order to evaluate the osteotoxic effects of 3-MC on bone growth, fertilized eggs (approx. 200 eggs) were transferred into a 1-L nursing tank with static water conditions. Methylene blue (0.0002% w/v) was added to prevent fungal growth. At 3 dpf, larvae were transferred into 6-well plates (15 larvae per well in 10 mL of fish water) and exposed to either 3-MC (concentrations ranging from 0.001 to 31.6 mg/L), calcitriol (1 α ,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃; Sigma-Aldrich), or 0.1% DMSO or ethanol (vehicle for 3-MC and calcitriol, respectively). About 70% of the fish water was renewed daily until the end of the treatment. At 6 dpf, larvae were sacrificed with a lethal dose of anesthetic (1000 ppm of 2-phenoxyethanol; Sigma-Aldrich), stained for 15 min at room temperature with 0.01% alizarin red S (AR-S) prepared in Milli-Q water (Millipore, pH 7.4), and washed twice with Milli-Q water for 5 min (method adapted from Bensimon-Brito et al., 2016). Stained larvae were then imaged and analyzed morphometrically using ImageJ 1.50e built-in tools (Schneider et al., 2012) as described in Tarasco et al., 2017.

Zebrafish skeleton development assay

In order to evaluate the osteotoxic effects of 3-MC on skeleton development, fertilized eggs (60 per condition) were transferred into 0.5-L plastic cups containing approximately 350 mL of EM supplemented with DMSO (vehicle) or 3-MC (concentrations ranging from 27 ng/L to 27 μ g/L). EM was renewed daily and dead eggs/embryos were counted and removed. At 20 dpf, larvae were given a lethal dose of anesthetic and total length was determined. Larvae were then fixed at 4°C for 24 h in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA; Sigma-Aldrich) prepared in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS at pH 7.4) and double stained with alizarin red S and alcian blue 8GX (AB) following a protocol adapted from Walker and Kimmel (2007). Larvae were

then imaged under bright-field light using a G12 PowerShot camera (Canon) and skeletal deformities were recorded.

Juvenile zebrafish culture and caudal fin amputation

Juvenile zebrafish were raised until 3 months old at 28°C in a closed system with recirculating water filtered through a high pore nylon mesh and an activated carbon filter, and under a 10:14 h dark/light photoperiod. Juveniles were anesthetized with 0.16 g/L of tricaine (MS-222, Sigma-Aldrich) and placed on the stage of a stereomicroscope. Caudal fin was carefully deployed and flattened then ventral lobe was amputated using a sterile scalpel in a single downward movement. Fish were allowed to recover and then placed into 1-L plastic cups (5 fish per cup) containing 3-MC (concentration ranging from 0.001 to 10 mg/L) diluted in fish water. About 70% of the fish water was renewed every second day until the end of the treatment. At 5 days post-amputation (dpa), fish were given a lethal dose of anesthetic (see above) and the caudal peduncle was collected, washed once with PBS, fixed in 4% PFA for 24 h at 4°C, washed again with PBS (3 times) then stained for 1 h with 0.1% AR-S in 0.2% KOH. Fin regeneration and *de novo* bone mineralization were assessed through imaging and morphometric analysis of regenerated areas as described in Cardeira et al., 2016.

Activity of signaling pathways

Because luciferase activity measured upon exposure of VSA13 cells to DMSO (vehicle) and 3-MC (0.1 mg/L) remained close to background values (including positive controls), suggesting that delivery of the DNA constructs into gilthead seabream cells by reverse transfection failed or was poorly efficient, an observation consistent with the hard-to-transfect status of fish skeletal cell lines (Marques et al., 2016; Collet et al., 2017), mineralogenic cell lines ATDC5 (mouse chondroprogenitor cells) and MC3T3-E1 (mouse osteoblast precursor

cells) were used to host the reporter constructs. ATDC5 and MC3T3-E1 cells were cultured as described by the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC) and sub-confluent cultures were reverse-transfected with reporter constructs of the Cignal 45-pathway reporter array (QIAGEN) according to manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, each well of the Cignal 96-well plate containing the 45 reporter constructs received sequentially 50 μ L of Opti-MEM (Life Technologies), 0.6 μ L of Attractene transfection reagent (QIAGEN) diluted in 50 μ L of Opti-MEM and 50 μ L of cell suspension (8×10^5 cells per mL of Opti-MEM supplemented with 10% of FBS and 1% of non-essential amino acid mixture (NEAA) from Life Technologies). Cells were incubated for 20 h at 37 °C under a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere then exposed to DMSO (vehicle) or 3-MC (0.1 mg/L) for 20 h in Opti-MEM supplemented with 0.5% FBS, 1% NEAA and 100 U/mL of penicillin/streptomycin (Life Technologies). Firefly and Renilla luciferase activities were determined in cell extracts using the Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay system (Promega) and a Synergy 4 multiplate reader (BioTek).

RNA extraction and quantitative real-time PCR

Zebrafish larvae at the age of 3 dpf were separated into 6 well-plates (20 larvae in 10 mL of water per well) and exposed for 3 days to 10 mg/L of 3-MC and its respective control (0.1% DMSO), with treatments renewed daily. Total RNA was extracted from 3 biological replicates of 6-dpf larvae stored in TRI-Reagent (Sigma Aldrich), following manufacturer's instructions. RNA integrity and quantity was confirmed using Experion Automated Electrophoresis system (Bio-Rad). Total RNA (1 μ g) was reverse-transcribed for 1 h at 37 °C using M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen), oligo-d(T) primer and RiboLock RNase Inhibitor (Thermo Scientific). All quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) reactions were performed using SensiFAST SYBR Hi-ROX kit (Bioline), 10 μ M of isoform-specific primers (Table 2 and Supplementary Table 1) and 1:10 dilution of reverse-transcribed RNA, in a CFX Connect

Real-Time PCR detection system (Bio-Rad). PCR amplification was as follows: an initial denaturation step of 2 min at 95°C and 40 cycles of amplification (10 s at 95°C and 20 s at 65°C). Efficiency of amplification was above 95 % for all primer sets. Levels of gene expression were calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ comparative method (Pfaffl, 2001) and normalized using the average of three housekeeping genes (i.e. *ef1a*, *actb1* and *rps18*).

Results and discussion

Mineralogenic and osteogenic effect of 3-MC

Mineralizing cultures of VSa13 cells were exposed chronically for 2 weeks to 0.1 mg/L of 3-MC (higher concentrations were found to be cytotoxic; results not shown) and the deposition of calcium-phosphate minerals within the extracellular matrix was assessed through AR-S staining and quantification (Fig. 1a). The mineral content in cultures exposed to 3-MC was found to be 62 ± 10 % lower than in control cultures, indicating that 3-MC has an anti-mineralogenic effect in fish bone-derived cells. Data reported in mammalian cell systems also showed a reduction of calcium deposition in rat osteoblast-like (ROB) and mouse pre-osteoblastic (MC3T3-E1) cell cultures exposed to 3-MC (Naruse et al., 2002), and we propose that mechanisms underlying the anti-mineralogenic effect of 3-MC may have been conserved throughout vertebrate evolution, although this will have to be confirmed. To further evaluate the osteogenic effects of 3-MC, zebrafish larvae at 3 dpf were exposed for 3 days to several concentrations of 3-MC (i.e. 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10 and 31.6 mg/L) and treatments were renewed every day until 6 dpf, when larvae were imaged and effects on the operculum area were determined. In all experiments, calcitriol (10 pg/mL) was used as positive control for osteogenic effect and found, as expected, to increase operculum size by 56.2 ± 9.0 % (Fig. 1b). While fish exposed to the lowest concentrations of 3-MC did not show any effect on the operculum development (i.e. 0.001, 0.01 and 0.1 mg/L), an anti-osteogenic

effect was observed at 1, 10 and 31.6 mg/L, decreasing the area of the operculum of 10.6 ± 3.8 , 21.2 ± 3.9 and 47.0 ± 4.6 %, respectively in an apparent dose dependence. Larvae exposed at the highest concentrations tested in this study (31.6 mg/L) exhibited a slight delay in their development as seen from area of the head measurements (results not shown) suggesting that the strong decrease of the operculum area at this concentration might be also related to growth retardation and not only to an osteotoxic effect of 3-MC. To further investigate the effects of 3-MC on bone formation, zebrafish juveniles regenerating their caudal fin were exposed for 5 days to several concentrations of 3-MC (concentrations higher than 10 mg/L affected fish survival; results not shown). Calcification of regenerating bony structures was assessed through AR-S staining (Fig. 1c). Anti-osteogenic effect of 3-MC, i.e. a decrease in the calcification of regenerating rays, was observed for concentrations equal or higher than 0.01 mg/L. While fin regeneration was normal in fish exposed to 0.01-1 mg/L of 3-MC, it was delayed in fish exposed to the highest concentration (see top panel of Fig. 1c), and we cannot exclude that, in this case, delayed calcification may be the result of a hindered regeneration process.

Although this hypothesis should be further investigated, e.g. using transgenic zebrafish lines expressing fluorescent proteins under the control of promoters for osteoblast marker genes (e.g. *runx2*, *osterix/sp7* and *osteocalcin*), we propose that delayed operculum formation in larvae and fin ray regeneration in juvenile fish exposed to 3-MC may result from an inhibition of osteoblast proliferation and differentiation as previously reported in mice (Naruse et al., 2002).

Skeletogenic effect of 3-MC

Zebrafish eggs were exposed chronically to 3-MC from fertilization until 20 dpf, then skeleton formation and deformities were assessed through AR-S / AB whole-mount double

staining (Fig. 2). Exposure to 3-MC concentrations higher than 27 $\mu\text{g/L}$ affected hatching rate and/or fish survival (results not shown) and only concentrations ranging from 27 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 27 ng/L were further tested. While none of these concentrations affected larval growth (assessed through the measurement of fish total length at 20 dpf; results not shown), 27 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of 3-MC increased by approximately 47% the number of fish larvae exhibiting skeletal deformities. However, the number of abnormal structures in deformed fish was similar in control and exposed fish (Table 1), with few multiple deformities observed. Deformities in fish exposed to 3-MC affected several skeletal structures, e.g. caudal fin vertebrae, branchial arches, operculum, urostyle, notochord, parhypural and hypurals (Fig. 2), but no particular pattern or prevalence of one type of deformity was identified. Future studies should aim at identifying mechanisms underlying the skeletogenic effects of 3-MC. The reported action of 3-MC on osteoclast and osteoblast function in mice (Naruse et al., 2002 & 2004) indicates that bone remodeling, i.e. the concerted action of bone resorption by osteoclast and bone formation by osteoblast, may be affected. A defective bone remodeling can lead to the development of a variety of skeletal disorders in mammals (Raisz, 1999) but also in fish (Witten and Huysseune, 2009; Ytteborg et al., 2010). Although this hypothesis should be further investigated, we propose that 3-MC potentiates the appearance of skeletal deformities through its action on bone remodeling. Incardona et al. (2004) reported that zebrafish larvae exposed to 2-4 ring PAHs exhibited dorsal curvatures and craniofacial deformities as a consequence of cardiac dysfunction; the hypothesis that 3-MC-induced skeletal deformities could be related to a cardiotoxic effect rather than an osteotoxic effect should therefore not be discarded. Finally, despite not being life-threatening for larvae, the type of deformities observed upon exposure to 3-MC may influence swimming and feeding activities in adult fish and reduce welfare and/or life expectancy.

3-Methylcholanthrene activates XRE/AhR signaling pathway

CIGNAL cell-based reporter assay was used to monitor the regulation by 3-MC (0.1 mg/L) of the activity of 45 signaling pathways involved in processes central to cell biology (see manufacturer's website for details). Because cellular hosts of fish origin were found not to be suitable for this analysis (see rationale in the materials and methods section), mouse ATDC5 chondroprogenitor cells and MC3T3-E1 osteoblast precursor cells were used to further investigate the mechanisms underlying 3-MC mineralogenic effects. While the activity of various signaling pathways was detected in both cell lines (29 pathways in MC3T3-E1 and 19 in ATDC5), only the activity of the xenobiotic pathway was significantly increased by 3-MC in both cell lines (23 times in MC3T3-E1 and 12 times in ATDC5; Fig. 3). In this pathway, xenobiotic responsive element (XRE) is activated through the binding of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR), a ligand-activated transcription factor involved in the intracellular signaling of many xenobiotics including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons such as 3-MC (Dietrich et al., 2016). Besides mediating xenobiotic toxic effects, AHR has been shown to be a relevant regulator of several physiological and pathological processes, e.g. hematopoiesis, inflammation, immune response, detoxification and cancer (see reviews by Barouki et al., 2012, Stockinger et al., 2014 and Murray et al., 2014 and references therein). AHR is expressed in osteoclasts and osteoblasts (Ilvesaro et al., 2005) and plays a physiological role in bone metabolism, i.e. bone resorption by osteoclast (Yu et al., 2015), and bone formation by osteoblast (Singh et al., 2000). In this regard, AHR stimulates osteoclastogenesis in mouse through the RANK/c-Fos signaling axis, and the benzo[*a*]pyrene, a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon formed during the incomplete combustion of organic matter, was shown to interfere with this signaling pathway (Izawa et al., 2016). Also in mouse, AHR was shown to inhibit osteoblastogenesis through the ERK signaling pathways upon TCDD exposure (Yu et al., 2014). AHR is also widely expressed in chondrocytes (Cedervall et al., 2015) and

participates in chondrogenesis (Kung et al., 2012) and cartilage homeostasis (Xiong et al., 2008; Cedervall et al., 2015). Given the central role of AHR in skeletal tissue, any molecules interfering with AHR signaling pathway will certainly disturb mechanisms underlying their formation and homeostasis, as reported for 2,3,7,8-TCDD which impaired ECM remodeling in regenerating zebrafish fin (Andreasen et al., 2007). We propose that osteotoxicity of 3-MC reported in fish (this work) is probably the direct consequence of the alteration of AHR signaling and transcriptional activity in bone and cartilage cell types. Whether altered regulatory activity of AHR directly affects the expression of bone and cartilage marker genes or indirectly interferes with the activity of pathways involved in bone and cartilage processes, e.g. Wnt (Schneider et al., 2014), HIF (Vorrink and Domann, 2014) and ER (Shanle and Xu, 2011) signaling pathways, remains to be determined, albeit no regulatory crosstalk could be clearly evidenced using the cell-based CIGNAL array.

Zebrafish gene expression

To further investigate the mechanisms underlying 3-MC toxicity in zebrafish, the expression of several marker genes involved in xenobiotic metabolism (*ahr2*, *pxr*, *cyp1a* and *gstp1*), osteoblast differentiation (*coll10a1*, *runx2b*, *sp7*, *fgf20a* and *bmp2b*), ECM mineralization (*oc1*, *oc2*, *alpl*, *spp1*) and degradation (*mmp9* and *mmp13*), bone signaling (*vdra*, *vdrb* and *fgf23*) and osteoclast activity (*acp5b* and *mmp9*) was determined by qPCR in larvae exposed to 3-MC (10 mg/L) for 3 days.

In agreement with the results of the CIGNAL assay, a 5.5-fold increase in *ahr2* expression was observed in larvae exposed to 3-MC, confirming the role of aryl hydrocarbon receptors in 3-MC-induced toxicity in zebrafish. A role of the pregnane X receptor, another xenobiotic-sensing receptor (Pavek, 2016), which signaling activity was not evaluated in the CIGNAL assay, was also evidenced by the 2.7-fold increase in *pxr xl* expression (a 3.1-fold increase in

pxr x2 expression was also observed although not statistically significant; Supplementary Fig. 1). Both Ahr2 and Pxr are ligand-dependent transcription factors that regulate the expression of xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes to protect the organism from exogenous and endogenous toxic chemicals (Kubota et al., 2014; Pavek, 2016). In this regard, the expression of both *cyp1a* and *gstp1*, which encode phase I (cytochrome P450, family 1, subfamily A) and phase II (glutathione S-transferase pi 1) enzymes involved in the metabolism and detoxification of xenobiotics, including PAH (Kung et al., 2012; Zanger and Schwab, 2013), was strongly up-regulated by 560 and 13.0 times, respectively, indicating their role in the response of zebrafish larvae to 3-MC exposure. The reduced expression of *Coll0a1* (5.9 folds), a marker of early osteoblasts in fish (Renn and Winkler, 2010; Kim et al., 2013), and the increased expression of *fgf20a* (3.0 times), a gene regulating bone cell activity in adult zebrafish and cell dedifferentiation during fin regeneration (Whitehead et al., 2005; Knopf et al., 2011; Cooper et al., 2013), suggests that 3-MC may inhibit osteoblast differentiation. Furthermore, the increased expression of *acp5b* (2.7 times) and *mmp9* (19.6 times), markers of osteoclast activity and of ECM degradation in zebrafish (Witten and Huysseune, 2009; de Vrieze et al., 2011; Sharif et al., 2014), suggests that 3-MC may stimulate osteoclast activity. An inhibition of osteoblast activity and/or a stimulation of osteoclast activity would support our hypothesis that 3-MC potentiates the appearance of skeletal deformities (see above) through its action on bone remodeling but also could explain the reduction in opercular bone growth, and the inhibition of extracellular matrix mineralization and *de novo* bone formation in regenerating caudal fin observed upon exposure to 3-MC. Future studies should aim at confirming whole-larvae differential gene expression in skeletal tissues of zebrafish exposed to 3-MC (e.g. by *in situ* hybridization and tissue-specific analysis of gene expression or by using transgenic reporter lines for bone-specific genes). Additional studies should also investigate the roles of *bmp2b* (2.2-fold increase), *alpl* (3.0-fold increase) and *vdrb* (2.8-fold

increase) in mechanisms underlying 3-MC osteotoxicity and whether their increased expression could be related to a feedback regulatory loop in osteoblast to increase mineralization in response to 3-MC effect on bone. The possibility that increased expression of *alpl*, the liver/kidney/bone alkaline phosphatase, is related to liver damage by 3-MC, as reported for other PAH (Haque et al., 2017), should not be discarded. A simple overview of the mechanisms of 3-MC osteotoxicity in zebrafish is presented in the Fig. 5, where the activation of AHR and PXR signaling pathways regulates not only the expression of xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes in liver and probably in other tissues given the ubiquitous expression of these genes in zebrafish (see their EST profile in the UniGene/NCBI database) but also genes involved in the differentiation and function of bone forming and resorbing cells.

Conclusions and perspectives

Data presented in this study demonstrated mineralogenic, osteogenic and skeletogenic effects of 3-methylcholanthrene, a chemical from the family of the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, in fish systems. For reasons that remain to be determined but could be related to differences in the complexity of the biological systems (from cultured cells to whole organism) and/or the duration of the treatment (from 3 days to 2 weeks), the concentrations of 3-MC needed to trigger a biological effect were remarkably different, ranging from 0.01 to 1 mg/L, all conceivable concentrations of PAHs in the environment (see for example Irwin et al., 1998; Dupree and Ahrens, 2007; Jahin et al., 2009; Moja et al., 2013). Gene expression data also indicated that Ahr2 and Pxr signaling pathways may be involved in the mechanisms underlying 3-MC toxicity in zebrafish and that altered osteoblast differentiation and/or osteoclast activity could explain its toxic effect in calcified tissues. Future studies should aim at exploring further the mechanisms of 3-MC osteotoxicity, in particular the

possible crosstalk between Ahr and Pxr pathways and whether mechanisms of toxicity are similar in the different systems used in this study. In a more global ecotoxicological context, it would be of utmost interest to investigate whether pollutants of the PAH family have a similar effect on fish bone. In this regard, preliminary data indicating reduced bone regeneration in adult zebrafish exposed to benzo[*a*]pyrene and increased occurrence of skeletal deformities in zebrafish larvae exposed to naphthalene (V. Laizé personal communication) suggests a widespread osteotoxicity of PAHs. Finally, this work demonstrated the suitability of fish systems to evaluate osteotoxicity of environmental pollutants.

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Table 1. Number of deformed fish per condition and number of deformities per deformed fish.

[3-MC] (No. of fish)	Normal fish	Deformed fish	No. of deformities		
			1	2	+3
Control (n=11)	7 (63.6%)	4 (36.4%)	4	0	0
27 µg/L (n=6)	1 (16.7%)*	5 (83.3%)	4	1	0
2.7 µg/L (n=9)	5 (55.6%)	4 (44.4%)	4	0	0
0.27 µg/L (n=8)	4 (50.0%)	4 (50.0%)	3	1	0
27 ng/L (n=9)	5 (55.6%)	4 (44.4%)	4	0	0

*significantly different from control (chi-squared test, 1 degree of freedom, $P=0.05$)

Table 2. Gene-specific primers used to analyze gene expression by qPCR.

Genes	Sequence (5'-3') ^a
<i>cyp1a</i>	Fw: CTGCGAACATTTTCAACGGTG
	Rev: CCATCGGCTTTCATAACAGAGTG
<i>ahr2</i>	Fw: CCAACAACCATCAATCAGTCAGAAC
	Rev: TGCCAGCCAGGCGGTCCTGC
<i>gstp1</i>	Fw: GTGCTGTTTCAGTCCAACGCC
	Rev: CGTCGTTTCATCACGTCAATGAGGG
<i>fgf20a</i>	Fw: GTTCAGGGAGCAGTTTGAGGAG
	Rev: CCATCTTTGTTGAGGGCTACATAATAAT
<i>pxr x1</i>	Fw: TAGGCAACGGCAGCATTCCG
	Rev: CATCACGAGCAGACACGGCG
<i>mmp9</i>	Fw: CTGAACCCACTGCTCCTCAACC
	Rev: CCGTCCTTGAAGAAGTGAAGCTCC
<i>vdrb</i>	Fw: TCAAGTGCCAGATGAGTTCGACC
	Rev: TGAAGAAGCCTTTCAGCCCT
<i>col10a1a</i>	Fw: ATACCCAGTTCTTGTCAAAAGTCCA
	Rev: GATCATAATGCTGCTCTGCGTT
<i>acp5b</i>	Fw: GTGGTTGGTCACTATCCCATCTG
	Rev: GAACGAACTCCCATCATCCTCTCT
<i>bmp2b</i>	Fw: GAGGAACTTAGGAGACGACGGGAACGC
	Rev: TCTCGGGAATGAGTCCAACGGCAC
<i>alpl</i>	Fw: TTCCTCTGCGGTGTCAAAGCCAA
	Rev: AAGCAGCACTCGGGGTGGCAT

Figure 1. (a) Extracellular matrix mineralization of gilthead seabream mineralogenic cell line VSa13 upon exposure to 0.1 mg/L of 3-MC. Mineral deposition was assessed after 2 weeks of treatment through alizarin red S staining (representative pictures of 2 replicates are presented in *top panel*) and spectrophotometric quantification (*bottom panel*). Values are the mean \pm SEM (n=4); (b) Effect of 3-MC on the operculum of 6-dpf zebrafish larvae. Area of the operculum was determined through morphometric analysis of AR-S stained larvae and corrected by the area of the head. DMSO and ethanol were used as vehicle for 3-MC and

calcitriol, respectively. *Asterisks* indicate values statistically different from vehicle values (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test for 3-MC and DMSO, Student's *t* test for calcitriol and ethanol; ** $p < 0.01$; **** $p < 0.0001$). Values are presented as mean \pm SEM ($n \geq 15$). Representative images of AR-S stained operculum are included on the top part of the figure for DMSO, and 1 and 10 mg/L of 3-MC. Bar is 50 μ m. (c) *De novo* bone formation in regenerating zebrafish caudal fin upon exposure to different concentrations of 3-MC. Calcification of forming bony structures was assessed at 5 days post-amputation through alizarin red S staining (representative pictures are presented in *top panel*) and morphometric quantification (*bottom panel*). Values are the mean \pm SEM ($n = 5$). Solid line indicates amputation line; dotted and dashed lines indicate areas of regeneration and calcification, respectively. *Asterisks* indicate values significantly different from control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test, $p < 0.05$). Bar is 0.5 mm.

Figure 2. Cranial region of 20-dpf zebrafish larvae double stained with alizarin red S and alcian blue. (a) control fish; (b,c) fish exposed to 2.7 μ g/L and 27 ng/L of 3-MC for 20 days. *Black arrows* indicate deformed opercula; *white arrows* indicate deformed branchial arches. Bar is 500 μ m.

Figure 3. Activity of signaling pathways altered upon exposure of mineralogenic cell lines MC3T3-E1 and ATDC5 to 3-methylcholanthrene. Cells were reverse-transfected by reporter constructs of the Cignal 45-pathway reporter array (see description of the array at www.sabiosciences.com) and exposed to DMSO (vehicle) or 0.1 mg/L 3-MC for 20 h. Signaling activities were inferred from firefly luciferase activity normalized with Renilla luciferase activity. Results are presented as fold changes of luciferase values in treated *versus* control cells \pm SEM. *Asterisks* indicate values significantly different (one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 4. Effects of 3-MC on gene expression. Zebrafish larvae were treated from 3 to 6 dpf with 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of 3-MC. The averaged expression of *ef1a*, *actb1* and *rps18* housekeeping genes was used to normalize the expression levels of selected genes. Values are the mean \pm SD of 3 biological replicates. Asterisks indicate values statistically different (Student's *t*-test; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$).

Figure 5. Schematic overview of the possible mechanisms underlying the toxic effect of 3-MC in zebrafish larvae. *Vertical arrows* after gene names indicate increased (upward pointing arrow) and decreased (downward pointing arrow) gene expression. *Question marks* indicate mechanisms not supported by published data and therefore speculative.

Supplementary Table 1. Gene-specific primers used to analyze gene expression by qPCR.

Genes	Sequence (5'-3')
<i>runx2b</i>	Fw: TCAGGAATGCCTCAGGGGTATG
	Rev: CTTGCGGTGGGTTTGTGAATACT
<i>oc1</i>	Fw: TTTATAGGCGGCGATGATTCC
	Rev: GAAGCGAACATGAAGAGTCTGACAGTCC
<i>oc2</i>	Fw: CCAACTCCGCATCAGACTCCGCATCA
	Rev: AGCAACACTCCGCTTCAGCAGCACAT
<i>sp7</i>	Fw: GCTAAGTCCAGGGCAGGCTCAG
	Rev: CAATGGCGTGAAATCAGGAGTGTAAC
<i>spp1</i>	Fw: GAACCTACACAGACCACGCCAACAG
	Rev: GGTAGCCCAAACACTGTCTCCCCG
<i>mmp13</i>	Fw: TGTCAAGTGGCAGAGGTGGATGACTC
	Rev: CGCCACCAGGAACAGATTGTAATATTGAG
<i>vdra</i>	Fw: GAATCCACAGTAAACGGTGATGCC
	Rev: TCATACTGCGCCTGAAGAAAACCC
<i>pxr x2</i>	Fw: TGCCCTGAAGAACACACTGC
	Rev: TCAACGGCGGAATGCTGAAA
<i>fgf23</i>	Fw: CATCCACCTTCAGACCACTTCAGAC
	Rev: TTCACTCCAAATATCGCCAGACGG

Supplementary Figure 1. Effects of 3-MC on gene expression. Zebrafish larvae were treated from 3 to 6 dpf with 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of 3-MC. The averaged expression of *efla*, *actb1* and *rps18* housekeeping genes was used to normalize the expression levels of selected genes. Values are the mean \pm SD of 3 biological replicates.